

ANISOGRID LATTICE STRUCTURE FOR AN INNOVATIVE COMPOSITE USV FUSELAGE

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ABSTRACT

In this paper a brief overview of the technological project ICCS (Innovative Composite Cold Structure) is provided with a focus on the methods and approaches that are being developed for the optimal design and prospectively the manufacturing of an innovative anisogrid lattice structure for the fuselage (cold structure) of an unmanned space re-entry vehicle (USV). This application involves the development of several theoretical, numerical, and experimental aspects for composite grid structures including modelling, manufacturing feasibility, and compliance with critical design requirements and mass targets.

One of the main challenging aspects undertaken in this project concerns the complexity of the reference fuselage shape, which may consist in an overall non-axisymmetric shell with single and double-curvature sections. In any case, a geodesic design is foreseen for helical ribs which are interlaced with hoop ribs in order to achieve a relatively dense and possibly regular pattern. The constraint on geodesic trajectories is required by the deposition process which is based on dry robotic winding (completed with resin infusion). Other peculiar aspects are related to the set of design requirements which follow from the space launcher, e.g., the restriction on first natural frequencies of the spacecraft. The other main issue is clearly referred to the coupling between the composite cold structure and the thermal protection system.

This study is in particular referred to the configuration of the vehicle that is being developed at CIRA (USV3) for which a baseline composite design solution exists in a preliminary form based on a conventional architecture including sandwich. The anisogrid solution is thus compared to this benchmark solution under the same basic requirements and material. The weight saving close to 20% is anticipated for the anisogrid fuselage that, in conjunction with a low-cost manufacturing approach, suggests a remarkable competitiveness of the overall concept.

1 INTRODUCTION

The interest on composite anisogrid lattice structures is notably increasing in the last few years, extending the range of possible efficient use. The well-known original Russian application is focused on axisymmetric cylindrical or conical shells optimized to sustain axial compressive and bending loads that are typical of space launcher primary structures (i.e., interstage and cone adapter). The possibility to extend efficient design and manufacturing methods to more complex shapes and additional requirements is investigated in the ICCS project. The complete description of the activities is beyond the scope of this paper: only the main points will be here discussed.

At the beginning of the project, the question of the proper selection of the reference vehicle was still open. Although the IXV programme was mature enough to provide a solid background [1], the opportunity to generalize design and manufacturing achievements was not so wide due to its peculiar aeroshape (Figure 1). On the other hand, the USV3 vehicle - which was being developed under a feasibility system study conducted at CIRA - was very appealing because of the more conventional and tapered aeroshape from one side but including all the sort of challenging aspects from the other side. In fact, this fuselage consists in a single curvature non-axisymmetric shell for the rear section, and in a double curvature non-axisymmetric shell for the forward section up to the nose. Moreover, additional requirements that were not included in the IXV experience were instead present in this

programme, like the integration of wing structures and landing gears. For these reasons, the USV3 was selected as the reference vehicle for the ICCS project.

Figure 1: IXV (left) and USV3-FTB3 (right) aerodynamic shape

Hence, in order to provide a competitive benchmark solution in composite material, a preliminary design study was initiated. With this aim, and following the experience of IXV, the sandwich structure with aluminium core was suggested as the baseline design concept (but not limited to this) for the benchmark solution. For a meaningful comparison, the same basic material was in principle adopted for both the benchmark and the grid solution. So, a CFRP prepreg with intermediate modulus - whose mechanical properties are well defined in commercial datasheet - was selected and applied to the benchmark design. The same kind of fibre and a similar resin system (for infusion) was then attributed to the design of the grid counterpart. Nevertheless, it is evident that the technique of interlaced tows exhibits a nominal fibre volumetric fraction in the ribs which is inherently lower (30-35%) than the standard layered version. This discrepancy, if not properly compensated, would produce an unrealistic solution for the grid concept. Unfortunately, this unusual fibre content does not meet any commercial datasheet. This lack of initial knowledge concerning mechanical properties of ribs can be partially recovered by specific literature and with the aid of micromechanics formulation (neglecting in any case specific manufacturing/tooling effects). However, it is indubitable that foregoing in-house experience represents a valuable guideline in order to link, since the beginning of the project, the expected performance with the technology. Some examples of basic mechanical properties derived from interlaced winding technology can be found in [2,3].

For the scope of the comparison, however, it was opportune to set a simple equivalence criterion between interlaced and layered materials and apply the same margin policy. The scope of such margin policy was to take into account possible degradation of strength properties (due to hygro-thermal effects, barely visible impact damages, statistic scattering, and so on) and arrive at a respective set of design allowables. This equivalence was finally established on the basis of a fictitious material having mechanical properties downgraded from the nominal values according to the lower fibre content. So, starting from nominal properties for the benchmark and downgraded properties for the grid, the same margin policy applied in USV3 was extended to the grid design.

In the following sections design and analysis approach for the anisogrid fuselage are described, whereas details on the benchmark solution can be found in [4]. The technological aspect related to the feasibility of mechanical interfaces joining the external C/SiC shingles with the internal anisogrid cold structure has been partially addressed and published in [5]. The study of vibro-acoustic and shock behaviour of grid panels are the subject of ongoing numerical and experimental activities.

2 DESIGN APPROACH

The most interesting aspect of the design of lattice shell structures is given by the multiplicity of possible configurations that are expressed in terms of the number of hoop and helical ribs and the cross-section of those ribs. According to the deposition process which is based on continuous robotic winding, a geodesic pattern is anticipated as the main design constraint for the trajectories of helical ribs, whereas hoop ribs are assumed to be coincident with the cross-section of the fuselage. In case of

conventional single-curvature (cylindrical or conical) axi-symmetric shells, with an assumed regular grid pattern, the issue of multiple configurations is facilitated by approximate closed form (minimum mass) solutions. Such solutions are developed under analytically formulated constraint equations that are representative of the strength and buckling behavior of the shell mainly subjected to axial compressive loads (see for example [6]). When more refined constraint equations or global stiffness requirements are introduced, the fully analytical approach is no longer efficient, and a numerical optimization procedure is needed to evaluate the performance of each configuration and to select the optimal solution [7,8]. In order to support this selection (before to proceed with more detailed modeling and analysis), it is very useful to have parametric routines that write the input file for FE analysis exploiting predetermined geodesic trajectories.

In case of a generic non-axisymmetric shell with various design requirements, the possibility to handle multiple configurations and predict the most promising ones is complicated by the fact that neither a set of approximate strength/buckling/stiffness constraint equations nor predetermined geodesic trajectories are available at the beginning of the design phase. For this reason, it is essential to apply some reasonable simplifications in terms of geometry and load cases and to understand the driving factors which may lead to the optimal solution.

Considering the information available at the beginning of the project, the launch phase was assumed as the driving load case for the initial design. During this phase several kinds of loads are transmitted to the spacecraft: quasi-static, dynamic, acoustic, shock. Moreover, in order to avoid dynamic coupling with the principal modes of the space launcher, the first bending and longitudinal modes of the spacecraft must comply with specific ranges [9]. This phase then involves at least buckling modes and strength of the rear section of the fuselage and the first natural frequencies of the complete vehicle. Further loads related to landing were only approximately verified in terms of maximum bending moment, whereas flight and thermal loads were premature and neglected in this initial design.

Constraint equations were then formulated in order to approximate some failure mechanisms according to the specific shape of the rear section of the fuselage. Since the rear section has the windward surface which is practically flat, this part is more prone to buckling than adjacent curved parts. In fact, assuming that the system of ribs is regularly distributed around the cross-section profile of the fuselage, the longitudinal inertia forces are shared proportionally to the length of the considered parts (irrespective of the specific configuration). For this reason, it is possible to evaluate the portion of axial compressive load which is taken by the flat surface. Similarly, the additional contribution given by the bending moment through transverse inertia forces can be calculated. At this point, it is possible to apply a formulation similar to as developed in [10] for the optimal design of flat anisogrid panels (without skin) in consideration of the compressive stress acting in helical ribs, the in-plane buckling of the cells, and the global buckling of the panel. In fact, under strength requirements, the contribution of the skin may be neglected. Nevertheless, the skin revealed itself to be essential in order to minimize the total mass of the structure. This acquisition, which is opposite to the optimal design of conventional grid structures, was deduced only after some optimization runs which included the first natural bending frequency of the vehicle as a constraint.

A representation of the overall design approach is given in Figure 2. In the center of this picture an optimization routine built in MATLAB handles constraint equations and inputs of different nature and approximation. The objective function is given by the minimization of the mass of the cold structure of the fuselage (grid+skin), whereas the total mass of the spacecraft is fixed at a target value of about 1500 kg, which clearly affects inertial loads and natural frequencies. Grid configurations are parametrically explored by fixing the number of hoop ribs and changing the number of helical ribs. The skin is added with an assumed stacking sequence and thickness. The optimization routine works separately on each configuration modifying three continuous variables (rib thickness, width of hoop and helical ribs) and finding respective suboptimal solutions. The presumed optimal design is searched among those suboptimal solutions. The selection of the final configuration is supported by relatively simple FE models which help to verify and improve the design constraints and eventually start new optimization runs with increased accuracy.

Figure 2: From basic requirements and simplifications to the optimal configuration

2.1 First natural frequency

In order to avoid dynamic coupling with the space launcher, the first bending frequency of the spacecraft in the launch configuration (that is, with the rear section fixed at the payload adapter), must reach at least 15 Hz. This requirement revealed itself critical not only for the grid solution but also for the benchmark. To address this requirement since the initial design phase it was necessary to introduce a semi-analytical formulation with the aid of some intermediate conceptual and modeling steps.

The first step was to simplify the first bending mode of the fuselage transforming the real geometry of the cold structure into an “equivalent” cylindrical shell with the same length as the fuselage and the circular section equal to the length of the rear cross-section profile. This modification determined only small deviations from the real values.

The second step was to approximate the bending mode of the cylindrical anisogrid shell assuming homogeneous orthotropic materials. In fact, the regular and dense system of ribs can be reduced to a set of equivalent smeared elastic properties (see for example [10]).

The third step was to adapt the analytical model valid for the first natural frequency of isotropic beams toward an orthotropic cylindrical shell. In this connection, parametric FE modal analyses indicated a progressive reduction of the first bending frequency of the shell by increasing the ratio E_x/G_{xy} , in which E_x and G_{xy} represent the longitudinal and in-plane shear modulus, respectively, of the orthotropic material. This effect is qualitatively explained by a global flexural mode which is progressively dominated by the shear deformation more than by the bending deformation. Knock-down coefficients with respect to the isotropic shell are blue starred in the plot of Figure 3. It can be seen that reduction of the frequency is quite significant for values of the ratio included in the range of practical interest, that is, up to 30, and becomes even severe above this range. In case of anisogrid structures, indeed, this ratio (expressed in terms of smeared elastic properties) depends mainly on the helical angle and can reach values 10 times higher than the isotropic case (that for an aluminum is about 2.6).

Figure 3: Knock-down factor of the first natural frequency wrt isotropic material

The fourth step was to express such effect in terms of a knock-down fitting function f_{KD} (red line in Figure 3) and adjust the model valid for isotropic beams. This fitting can be obtained with the aid of either a polynomial or an exponential function. Finally, the approximate first natural bending frequency can be supplied to the optimization routine as,

$$F_{bending} = 1.8751^2 \frac{R}{2\pi L^2} \sqrt{\frac{E_x}{2\rho}} f_{KD} \quad (1)$$

$$f_{KD} = f_{KD} \left(\frac{E_x}{G_{xy}} \right) \quad (2)$$

where R and L are the radius and the length of the equivalent cylindrical shell. We remark that this model is valid for a generic orthotropic material, that is, the thickness of the shell can be realized with skin, grid or a combination of both. The important thing is to properly express the mass density and the two equivalent elastic properties. In case of anisogrids without skin, equation 1 can be further specified as,

$$F_{bending} = 1.8751^2 \frac{R}{2\pi L^2} \cos^2 \varphi \sqrt{\frac{E\omega}{2\rho(\omega \sin \varphi + 1)(\sin^3 \varphi + \omega)}} f_{KD} \quad (3)$$

in which E , ρ , and ω represent respectively: the longitudinal modulus and the mass density of ribs, the width ratio between hoop and helical ribs.

At this point, even though it is possible to discriminate among various grid configurations of the fuselage, with and without the contribution of the skin, it is difficult to predict with a reasonable accuracy the first natural frequency of the overall spacecraft. The real vehicle, in fact, includes several concentrated and distributed nonstructural masses or structural masses that in any case do not participate significantly in the bending mode of interest (e.g., equipment, thermal protection system, substructures adjacent to the fuselage) other than many structural modifications and discontinuities that alter the initial regular arrangement (e.g., change of cross-section of ribs, wide openings and reinforcements). The effect of non-participating structural masses and especially of nonstructural masses greatly reduces the final frequency with the consequent risk to stay below the limit value. In order to approximate the overall mass effect, however, an assumption on the uniform distribution of such masses can still be made in order to project the final frequency according to a simple square root law. Nevertheless, there is no evidence on how close such predictions are to the real value.

In order to assess this aspect, it is necessary to characterize the natural frequency of the overall vehicle with realistic masses distribution and further elements that are not strictly related to the configuration of the fuselage. This final step provides a specific “model factor” which completes the estimation of the natural frequency with a good accuracy. At this point, this critical requirement can be better controlled in the preliminary design phase allowing to approach the most efficient configuration.

We note that the model factor found in this case is about 1.2, that is, the prediction of the first natural frequency based on the equivalent cylindrical grid structure with uniform stiffness and a uniform nonstructural mass distribution turns out to be 20% less than the better estimation of the final value which includes the most complications of the whole vehicle. Simplifications were overall conservative.

We remark that the same difficulty to reach the limit frequency was also found on the benchmark side. Here this problem was theoretically solved directly in the FE model by adding longitudinal unidirectional composite stiffeners embedded in the sandwich structure [4]. In the grid design, however, this fact was even more critical because, as remarked in introduction, the typical rib element has a low fiber content and thus relatively low stiffness. For this reason, the global stiffness of the shell is more efficiently increased by means of a thick skin made of angle plies than by the system of ribs (the skin has standard nominal properties). This outcome is completely different from the optimal design of usual lattice shell structures that are buckling-dominated and the role of the skin can be normally neglected. Conversely, a stiffness-dominated problem occurs in this case through the first natural frequency and the structural role of the skin turns out to be relatively important.

Figure 4: Simulation of the first bending mode of the spacecraft with anisogrid fuselage

3 ANALYSIS APPROACH

As described in Figure 1, the output of the preliminary design is an optimal configuration, based on simplified and regular models, eventually corroborated by a corresponding FE model and verification. Then, the selected configuration must be transferred and adjusted toward the real geometry of the shell, preserving the number of helical ribs (which are requested to be geodesic), the number of hoop ribs and the cross-section of ribs.

For this reason, much effort has been devoted in this project to find a method for the identification of geodesic trajectories on complex lattice shells and for the construction of corresponding finite-element models.

In fact, the passage from the simplified to the real geometry implies no particular modifications in case of single-curvature sections, like in the case of the rear part of the fuselage, where the angle with the meridian is the same for all the geodesic ribs and remains constant along the axis of the shell. Conversely, in double-curvature and non-axisymmetric sections (like the forward fuselage) the angle of geodesic paths is continuously changing; the rate of change is different for each rib and depends on the specific geometry.

In order to trace geodesic patterns on the complete shell, CAD software packages are available as a primary solution: here two main approaches are usually available to find *minimum distance* curves, which are geodesic trajectories, i.e. start-point/end-point and start-point/start-derivative.

In the former case, two points located on the shell (i.e., in two different sections) are connected by means of the minimum length trajectory searched by the software. This approach would in principle assure the uniform distribution of ribs around control sections of the fuselage, like for example in correspondence of flanges or end rings connecting two barrels. Nevertheless, the set of possible geodesic lines turning around the axis of the fuselage is not explored by this approach, which is limited to shortcuts only.

In the latter case, that is, start-point and derivative, initial values are fixed for each rib in correspondence of the initial section of the fuselage, and the software then computes the corresponding geodesic path along the shell. This approach does not guarantee the regularity of the helical ribs distribution around control sections of the fuselage. In any case, based on this experience, the CAD/FEM modelling is a viable path for the geodesic design only after geometry and configuration have been effectively and definitively frozen. The CAD modelling of the lattice fuselage itself represents a quite complicated and time-consuming task which is not particularly suitable in the preliminary design phase in order to accommodate small changes or drastic re-configuration of the structure. Thus, several procedures have been attempted in order to minimize the impact of manual operations in the CAD geodesic design and in successive FE modelling. Such activities can be grouped in three main procedures as summarized in the following Table:

	MATLAB Single-curvature	CAD/MATLAB	MATLAB Double-curvature
Applicability	Rear section	Full fuselage	Full fuselage
Main input	Sample points of the section profile	CAD model of the fuselage shell	Mesh (quad elements) of the fuselage shell
Generated mesh	ribs: BAR skin: CQUAD4	ribs: BAR skin: CQUAD4	ribs: BAR skin: CTRIA3
Impact of manual operations	Minimum	High	Low
Approach for geodesic trajectories	Start point and derivative	Start point and derivative	Start point/end point
Use in the ICCS project	Early studies and sizing	Initial anisogrid configuration	Final anisogrid configuration

Table 1: Main procedures implemented for geodesic design and FE modeling of the fuselage.

The first procedure is referred to the rear section of the fuselage which is a single-curvature shell.

This fact greatly simplifies the identification of geodesic trajectories. Developing the surface on a plane, it is straightforward to trace geodesic patterns and obtain the original surface by an inverse interpolation procedure which accounts for the real curvature of the section profile (Figure 5). The input is given by the profile and a certain number of control points of this profile. The routine is written in MATLAB and generates the finite-element models of the shell including 1D hoop and helical ribs (bar elements) and the skin with 2D quad elements. The routine is flexible, all the degrees of freedom are available and multiple configurations can be easily generated and verified. This approach allowed to conduct preliminary simulation studies and sizing, and to appreciate the driving aspects/requirements for the minimum mass design. Clearly, this approach does not include the complete fuselage but only a simplified version.

In order to overcome the limit of the first procedure, a mixed CAD-MATLAB procedure was attempted: the CAD is used for the identification and drawing of geodesic and hoop trajectories on the whole fuselage. Instead of transforming those lines in 3D solid ribs, 1D geodesic trajectories are passed to an interface and transformed into corresponding 1D finite-elements, whereas the skin is

separately meshed and then attached to the ribs by means of an additional routine that applies a merge criterion of nodes. However, not all the nodes are assured to be attached to the ribs. This procedure allows to preserve degrees of freedom for the design parameters related to ribs and skin. Nevertheless, change of configurations are not easily possible because CAD modelling is requested at every change of configuration with consequent manual operations in order to prepare the interface with MATLAB routines.

The third procedure is almost fully based on MATLAB routines developed ad hoc. The only external input is given by a 2D quad mesh of the skin of the shell representing the fuselage (or a specific section). Based on these nodal points, the procedure is able to find all the possible geodesic trajectories, including a certain number of rotations around the fuselages, implementing a specific optimization algorithm. With this approach, all possible lattice configurations of the whole fuselage can be automatically explored and generated in only few minutes (see an example in Figure 6).

The accuracy of the calculation of geodesic trajectories has been verified in light of the CAD modelling. Clearly, the practical use of this procedure is limited to the most promising ones (the screening of candidate solutions is made with the first procedure on simplified surface). The skin is transformed into 2D triangular elements which are consistently attached to all the nodes of the system of 1D ribs.

The first procedure was efficiently adopted in the early phase of the project supporting the initial design. At the same time, CAD and CAD/FEM modelling were conducted showing practical limits and drawbacks and the necessity to have more flexible tools to follow several input changes that are quite typical of the initial phase of each project. The third procedure was thus conceived and used as a more general method able to develop various configurations according to the change of general inputs. More details of this procedure are reported in the following subsection.

Once the design configuration has been finally assessed and the FE model has been built up, several manual operations are needed in order to introduce: local modifications, more robust hoop ribs in correspondence of concentrated loads (coming from wings and landing gears), main openings and reinforcements, substructures and interfaces, nonstructural masses. Iterative analyses with various load cases including landing and flight loads are necessary. The flow chart of this phase is described in Figure 7.

Figure 5: Example of FE modeling generated from the first procedure.

Figure 6: Example of FE modeling generated from the third procedure.

Figure 7: From the optimal configuration to the FE model

3.1 Geodesic Modelling

The basic winding problem is related to the *stability of paths* described by tensioned fibers on surfaces. The effect of internal tension in the single tow is a compaction force aligned along the osculating circle, towards its center, on each point of the path. Along a *geodesic* path on a surface, by definition, this normal to the path is aligned to the normal to the surface in the same point, so that the tensioned fiber has no force components which laterally deviate it from the deposited path.

The geodesic lines on a surface are, locally, *minimum length curves*, described in the two dimension coordinate domain by a not linear second order differential equation set, which can be integrated by imposing two constrain conditions. By integrating the set of equations, the coordinates $u(s)$ and $v(s)$ of curve $C(s)$ are determined, which is mapped by a geodesic $\Gamma(s)$ on the surface (Figure 8) [11].

Figure 8: Geodesic curve mapping

The grid winding problem refers to a single helical rib between two pins, and the two constraints for the equations are the positions on initial and ending pin [12].

The “absolute” minimum distance curve, which is geodesic, can be easily determined on the surface with several efficient algorithms based on Dijkstra method, usually implemented in CAD software packages.

Figure 9: Minimum distance and geodesic curve with a rotation

But geodesic curves are by definition *locally* minimum solutions, and may have different lengths, depending on the overall path, between the start and the end point. For example, on a closed cylinder, all the regular helices passing through two points are geodesic, and depending on the number of rotations around the closed cylinder, these curves may have different lengths (Figure 9). These curves are all *locally minimum distance* curves, i.e. geodesics, so that they are stable and windable, even if they are not the *absolute* minimal distance curve, which is the shortest helix, with no rotation around the surface.

Usually CAD software packages have not a clear and easy tool to manage the set of geodesics passing through two points with an assigned number of rotations around the shell, and this fact may limit the possibility to easily generate the possible configurations of grids to be examined in the design optimization.

Figure 10: Domain replicas and geodesic curves with rotations

To solve this problem, a tricky procedure has been implemented in MATLAB, based on the following steps:

- 1) the surface is meshed on a cylindrical system of coordinates (z, θ) , replicated along the θ a sufficient number of times to count the assigned number of rotations (Figure 10).
 - o 2) having fixed the start pin coordinates, and having chosen the end pin coordinates, in the selected replica of the map, a trial initial tangent direction is fixed; the integration of equations, based on initial position and tangent direction, gives a corresponding geodesic.
 - o 3) the distance between the trial geodesic line and the end pin position, in the replicated map, is evaluated.
- 4) an iteration of steps 2 and 3 is done toward the minimization (to zero) of this distance (shooting method)

By this method it is easily possible to explore all the geodesic trajectories, even if they rotate around the shell a finite number of times.

A further improvement aiming at a drastic reduction of the computational effort has been implemented, which substitutes steps 2,3 and 4 with the following

2') having fixed the start pin coordinates and the end pin coordinates in the selected replica of the map, a limited subdomain along trial tangent direction is fixed, which corresponds to an helical strip on the surface (Figure 11).

3') the absolute minimum distance curve on the strip portion of the surface is determined by the Dijkstra approach (no shortcuts are possible outside the strip).

Figure 11: Sub domain selection and geodesic curve with rotation

4 PRELIMINARY COMPARISON

The comparison between the benchmark and the grid design solution involves the same basic requirements and constraints and almost the same load cases. Margins of safety are relatively high for both solutions except for some local failures of minor importance. The critical stiffness requirement determines a robust skin in the central and rear section of the fuselage but allows to reduce the thickness in the forward section and to totally remove the skin just close to the nose section.

The grid design provides a cold structure that weighs roughly 10% of the overall mass target with a theoretical weight saving close to 20% with respect to the benchmark. Some mass increase is expected from the effect of wings structure interfaces that, by the way, were not conceived to accommodate the grid concept since the start. Some mass increase may also be expected from the benchmark side, since some failure mechanisms that are peculiar of the sandwich concept are not fully captured by implemented FE models. Moreover, thermal loads are not explicitly treated in this analysis, but only in connection with the maximum operative temperature of the cold structure which is fixed at 160°. In this regard, design activities are proceeding aiming at the sizing of mechanical interfaces between the thermal protection system of the windward surface and the grid cold structure. In this case, the presence of multiple hard points (the nodes of the grid) should in principle facilitate the junction with the shingles. In addition, the effect of residual stresses of the manufacturing process are not taken into account in this comparison. However, this preliminary comparison, with all the included approximations and lack of information from both benchmark and grid side, demonstrates the high competitiveness of the composite anisogrid concept and suggests to further investigate this technology.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The paper describes the objective, the approach and preliminary results concerning the design and prospectively the manufacturing of an innovative composite anisogrid structure for the fuselage (cold structure) of an unmanned space re-entry vehicle. Preliminary design and analysis tools have been constructed in order to handle multiple and complex structural configurations of the fuselage, specific design requirements and constraints aiming at minimum mass solutions. Implementation of light routines is crucial in the preliminary design phase in order to follow and adjust the change of main inputs (loads, shape, general requirements). The development of a parallel composite benchmark (the baseline) with the same assumption and requirements helps to assess the performance of the proposed innovative concept. The following main steps have been developed and implemented:

- An initial sizing, with the aim to understand basic aspects of minimum mass solutions and indicate the most promising configurations.
- Numerical procedures to identify geodesic trajectories and automatically build FE models with increasing complexity, including ribs and skin.
- Upgrade of the FE model (with nonstructural masses, openings, local changes, etc.) borrowed from the benchmark model for a realistic comparison. Iterative analysis and design upgrade.
- Inclusion of the USV3 margin policy.

Preliminary results suggest the weigh saving close to 20% with respect to the benchmark. With this encouraging outcome the project is now entering the experimental phase in order to substantiate design and manufacturing assumptions of the grid solution. This phase, in particular, is focused on the manufacturing and testing of flat anisogrid panels (with and without the skin) “extracted” from the windward of the fuselage. Once completed the Preliminary Design Review milestone, the experimental activity shall be devoted to the manufacturing and testing of technological demonstrators (fuselage sections) representative of the overall project.

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